

**THE PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION
TO THE STUDY OF THE TRAIID -N C-S-. PART VI.
ACTION OF NITROUS ACID ON α,β -METHYL-
PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDE.**

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The reaction has been studied to see the effect on the configuration of the thiocarbamide by (i) weak acid and (ii) strong acid. This is shown by the production of a nitroso derivative in (i) and an oxidation change in (ii). Under the conditions described half of the sulphur can be eliminated from the product of either change to result in the formation of a single base, $C_{10}H_{18}N_4S$.

The action of nitrous acid has been studied on phenyl-, and $\alpha\alpha'$ -methylphenylthiocarbamides (Mehta and Krall, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 635; Krall, *ibid.*, 1937, 14, 478). In both cases in the presence of weak acid the production of nitrogen and accompanying end-products suggested their normal behaviour as amides. On the other hand, in the presence of strong acid the change was mainly one of oxidation resulting in the formation of Hector's base in the first case and a formamidine disulphide in the second.

As an extension of this work the above reaction has been studied with α,β -methylphenylthiocarbamide.

When sodium nitrite reacts with the thiocarbamide in the presence of acetic acid, practically no gas is evolved and a nitroso derivative is formed thus:

The latter is decomposed by aqueous hydrochloric acid whereby nitric oxide is first evolved and then half of the sulphur is eliminated and the resulting solution yields a picrate from which the composition of the free base is deduced to be $C_{10}H_{18}N_4S$. The reaction, therefore, seems to be as follows:

The free base, however, is not obtained pure as it decomposes in solution into phenylmustard oil and a resinous basic nitrogenous substance. With alkali the above nitroso derivative evolves nitrogen and phenylmustard oil is the main product. The fact that thiocarbamide itself on treatment as in (A) does not react lends additional support for this mode of formation.

In the presence of hydrochloric acid, sodium nitrite reacts rapidly and produces initially an evanescent wine-red colour; nitric oxide (99%) is evolved and the solution gives a precipitate with aqueous picric acid. These facts indicate an oxidation change *e.g.*,

Varying amount of the nitroso derivative is always produced which is immediately decomposed in the acid reaction mixture. The base soon deposits half of the sulphur yielding another base which proves to be identical with the one obtained by decomposing the nitroso derivative with hydrochloric acid as in (B) above. The formation of nitroso derivative in the presence of a weak acid is an evidence for the existence of a thiocarbamide configuration, $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{HN}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NHMe}$. In the presence of strong acid, however, it is difficult to decide if the oxidation change referred to above is due to the conversion of the thiocarbamide into another tautomeride or else to the secondary decomposition of the nitroso derivative, because in either case the base obtained after elimination of sulphur happens to be identical.

In an attempt to synthesise diazothiols by oxidation of aromatic thiocarbamides with ferric chloride Chakervarti and De (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 661) observed the formation of mustard oils and guanidine derivatives. It is, therefore, tempting to suggest that the base $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{S}$ may be an intermediate product during the formation of the expected diazthiol. This is being investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of Nitrous Acid on $\alpha\beta$ -Methylphenylthiocarbamide in presence of Acetic Acid.—The thiocarbamide (8.3 g.) was dissolved in 50% warm alcohol (200 c. c.) in a beaker and one equivalent of 99.2% sodium nitrite (3.475 g.) in water (50 c. c.) was added. When crystallisation had just started, the beaker was put in a water-bath and 2*N*-acetic acid (100 c. c.) was added in two or three instalments. A yellow precipitate was soon obtained with little evolution of nitric oxide. After 1 hour it was isolated in almost pure

form (yield 10 g.) and was recrystallised by the slow evaporation of its ethereal solution in golden yellow needles, m. p. 84° (decomp.). (Found: S, 15.7. $C_8H_9ON_2S$ requires S, 16.1 per cent). The substance decomposes on keeping. The aqueous mother liquors smelt of phenylmustard oil and later deposited some needles, m.p. 137° (*vide infra*).

Decomposition of the Nitroso Derivative. (a) With Acid.—The nitroso derivative (4.9 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) was warmed with *N*-hydrochloric acid (200 c.c.) at 70–75° for 10 minutes. Nitric oxide was evolved and 0.39 g. of sulphur (half the theory, 0.4 g.) separated. The acid filtrate with alkali gave a base which could not be crystallised from the common solvents. In the dry state the precipitated base was fairly stable and melted at 82°. An alcoholic solution of the base (1.5 g.) and picric acid (1.2 g.) gave a picrate (cubes), m.p. 195°. [Found: N, 18.56; S, 6. $C_{16}H_{18}N_4S^+C_6H_2OH(NO_2)_3$ requires N, 18.6; S, 6.01 per cent]. On heating either alone or in solution the base decomposed into phenylmustard oil and a basic resinous substance. If an aqueous acidic solution of the base, as obtained after decomposing the nitroso derivative with hydrochloric acid, was treated with aqueous picric acid isomeric picrate was obtained. The latter crystallised from methyl alcohol (leaflets and needles) but decomposed on repeated crystallisation. [Found: N, 18.64; S, 6.1 per cent]. Its m.p. (153–54°) was slightly low due to the presence of traces of the isomer (cubes). Occasionally, under conditions not yet understood, the picrate, melting at 195°, was obtained even in this case.

(b) With Alkali.—The nitroso derivative (3.92 g.) was treated with cold *N*-sodium hydroxide (20 c.c.). Reaction began with the immediate evolution of nitrogen and the alkaline reaction mixture contained an oil (2.5 c.c.) smelling of mustard oil and isocyanide, and some sulphide. The separated oil after being washed with dilute hydrochloric acid gave phenylmustard oil (2.3 g.; theoretical 2.7 g.).

(c) With Water.—In aqueous alcoholic solution the nitroso derivative decomposed slowly evolving nitric oxide (58%), nitrogen (42%) and sulphur and phenylmustard oil were also formed. The latter seemed to disappear after some time and a nonbasic solid, m.p. 137°, containing S and N and stable to dilute alkali was also obtained.

Action of Sodium Nitrite on $\alpha\beta$ -Methylphenylthiocarbamide in presence of Hydrochloric Acid (Gas Phase).—The thiocarbamide (0.083 g.) was introduced into a Lunge's nitrometer with the help of 1 c.c. of alcohol, 1 c.c. of water and the mixture treated with 1 c.c. of 4*N*-hydrochloric acid and one equivalent of *N*-sodium nitrite (0.5 c.c.). The reaction was brisk and began with the production of a red colour and some yellow nitroso derivative

which decomposed after some time. Gas evolved (12.6 c. c. at 22° and 750 mm.) contained nitric oxide (99%). Excess of nitrous acid evolved more gas.

Action of Nitrous Acid on $\alpha\beta$ -Methylphenylthiocarbamide in presence of Hydrochloric Acid (neglecting the gas phase).—The thiocarbamide (4.5 g.) was dissolved in 50% warm alcohol (100 c. c.) and 4*N*-hydrochloric acid (50 c. c.) was added. When crystallisation commenced, the solution was put in a water-bath and treated with an equivalent of sodium nitrite (1.737 g.) in water (50 c. c.). The reaction began with the production of red colouration and some nitroso derivative. The latter also went in solution after some time. The clear solution was examined as follows:—

(i) 50 C. c. of the solution were neutralised with ammonia when an oil and later a solid appeared. The latter yielded sulphur partly on treatment with 4*N*-hydrochloric acid and partly from the acid solution so obtained.

(ii) 0.5 C. c. of the solution was treated with aqueous picric acid when a yellow precipitate (2 g.) was obtained. On crystallisation from methyl alcohol, however, sulphur separated and a picrate (needles and leaflets), m.p. 158° crystallised out. [Found: N, 18.65; S, 6.15. $C_{16}H_{16}N_4S \cdot C_6H_3(OH)_3$ requires N, 18.61; S, 6.01 per cent]. Mixed m.p. with the similar picrate obtained previously [*cf.* (a) p. 219] 155-56°.

(iii) 50 C. c. of the solution on standing (1 hour) or on warming at 80° deposited 0.086 g. of sulphur (theoretical 0.1 g.) and the resulting solution gave with aqueous picric acid the picrate, m.p. 153-54° identical with that in (ii).

(iv) 50 C. c. of the solution were warmed at 80° and filtered from separated sulphur (0.09 g.). The acid filtrate with alkali gave a base which in alcoholic solution gave the picrate (cubes), m. p. 195° with picric acid as in (a).